

Eurodoc Statement on Employment and Financial Conditions of ECRS

Investing in research and higher education is an investment in the future. Eurodoc emphasises the importance of national governments meeting the commitments of large public investments in the sector as had been set by both the EHEA and the ERA. This means **reaching the target of 1.25% of GDP for public spending**.

At the core of the policies of EHEA and ERA is the mobility of the academic community. It is thus crucial that legislation and other frameworks serve to facilitate mobility and exchange and ensure comparable employment conditions across Europe. Yet many systemic barriers remain and are exacerbated by the current nature of the research careers with its short term employment and the hurdles for obtaining (permanent) resident permits. Europe's desire for better and more brain circulation of EU citizens and third country nationals who pursue a research career should not come at the expense of their social security. In order to ensure Europe's competitiveness now and in the future, research careers and careers in higher education must be made more attractive *across* Europe. Eurodoc advocates for doctoral candidates, postdocs, and other early career researchers to receive **salaries and have social rights adequate to their qualifications that must include extensions for sick and/or parental leave as well as special needs allowances**.

Delivering on the promise of EHEA and ERA means:

- **recognising the professional status of doctoral candidates as researchers by ensuring they are formally employed.**
- **acknowledging** that doctoral candidates have a similar **level of training and length of professional experiences** as **upper secondary teachers** in their first years of employment.
- **ensuring that doctoral candidates** receive **salaries and social rights that are comparable to upper secondary teachers** in their first years of employment
- **ensuring that postdoctoral and other early career researchers are formally employed** and not on stipends or similar.
- **ensuring** that postdoctoral and other early career researchers receive **salaries adequate to their qualifications**.

About this statement

This statement was prepared by the board of Eurodoc 2024/2025 and adopted by the member organisations on the 26.05.2025

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Eurodoc, the European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers, is a grassroots federation of 26 national associations of early career researchers (ECRs) from 24 countries across Europe. Eurodoc was established in 2002 and is based in Brussels. As a representative of doctoral candidates and junior researchers at the European level, Eurodoc engages with all major stakeholders in research, higher education, and innovation in Europe.

